

IMPORTANCE OF MANAGEMENT IN EMERGENCY PREVENTION

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Annotatsiya: Maqolada O‘zbekiston Respublikasida favqulodda vaziyatlarning oldini olish uchun boshqaruv tizimini joriy qilish uchun xalqaro tadqiqotlar tahlili amalga oshirilgan. Bu yo‘nalishda keyinchalik amalga oshirilishi rejalashtirilgan vazifalar va ularning dolzarbligi ko‘rsatib o‘tilgan.

Kalit so‘zlar: boshqaruv tizimi, xavfni aniqlashtirish jarayoni, favqulodda vaziyat, monitoring va tekshiruv.

Аннотация: В статье проведен анализ международных исследований по внедрению системы управления предупреждением чрезвычайных ситуаций в Республике Узбекистан. В этом направлении обозначены задачи, которые планируется реализовать в дальнейшем, и их актуальность.

Ключевые слова: система управления, процесс идентификации рисков, чрезвычайная ситуация, мониторинг и проверка.

Abstract: In the article, an analysis of international studies on the introduction of a management system for the prevention of emergency situations in the Republic of Uzbekistan is carried out. In this direction, the tasks planned to be carried out later and their relevance are indicated.

Key words: management system, risk identification process, emergency situation, monitoring and inspection.

Natural and man-made emergency situations - an accident, disaster, dangerous natural phenomenon, natural disaster or other that can lead to or lead to the death of people in a certain area, damage to people's health or the natural environment, serious material losses and disruption of people's living conditions situations arising as a result

of a disaster, as a result of the spread of quarantine and other infectious diseases dangerous to humans [7].

In order to determine the forms and level of control in emergency situations, a number of scientific studies have been carried out on the high effectiveness of the use of the risk management system (Risk Management) by the Ministry of Emergency Situations in preventing emergencies.

Scientists such as I. Bashynska, Taleb Abdullah Mohammed Ali Alhammadi, Hamed Rashed Sayed Abdullah Alnuaimi analyzed the issue of using the risk management system in emergency situations and came to appropriate conclusions in their articles entitled "Risk management in emergency situations" [5].

Common signs of an emergency:

presence or threat of death;

significant deterioration of living conditions;

significant deterioration of human health and financial losses.

An important component of such management should be an emergency risk management system that includes four steps:

planning stage;

response stage;

softening stage [1].

Figure 1. Emergency management steps.

The problem of emergency management should be solved not only by restructuring the functional structure and improving the skills of management personnel, but also by transitioning to a new management paradigm [4].

Emergency risk assessment and management activities include the following tasks:

1. Formation of the information base of the risk management system.

2. Risk analysis and assessment:

- objects of risk analysis;

- risk indicators for risk analysis objects that determine the need to take measures to prevent and minimize risks;

- assessment of possible damage in the event of a hazard;

3. Development and implementation of risk management measures:

- the probability of risk occurrence and possible consequences;

- to apply the necessary measures to prevent and minimize risks.

The main tasks of the risk management system:

creation of a single information space that ensures the operation of the risk management system;

development of risk identification methods;

identifying potential risks and recording them;

to determine the causes and conditions contributing to the occurrence of emergency situations;

assessment of damage that can be caused by potential and identified risks;

determine the possibility of preventing or minimizing risks;

development and application of methods for evaluating the effectiveness of measures to be implemented;

development and implementation of risk prevention or minimization measures;

monitoring the implementation of measures to prevent or minimize risks;

evaluating the effectiveness of risk management measures and changing management decisions accordingly [6].

Figure 2. Standard process mechanism of the risk management system

The context definition process includes the identification (categorization) of external economic activity participants.

The process of risk identification is carried out to make the right decisions about the selection of control objects. The process of forming risk criteria should be based on the ability to identify the risk and quickly eliminate it. According to experts, the most important criteria are, first of all, the threat to human health and life, the fiscal situation, and losses during the delivery of goods.

Risk analysis - quantitative and (or) qualitative analysis evaluates the amount and probability of possible damage.

Risk assessment - evaluates the impact and consequences of the occurrence of a risk (eg: high, medium, low).

Elimination of the hazard - determines the appropriate measures for the identified hazard (eg: bypass, contain, eliminate the hazard).

I.A. Sheykin and A. Musani "Emergency preparedness and humanitarian action: the research deficit. Eastern Mediterranean Region perspective" researched and developed relevant recommendations on how to collect, store and analyze information

related to all hazards and natural disaster management to facilitate the use of high quality information by decision makers at all levels [2].

Summary. The introduction of the electronic system of emergency risk assessment and management in the Republic of Uzbekistan has a significant effect on protection against emergency situations. For this reason, it was decided to carry out research in the directions of forming the information base of the risk management system, analyzing and evaluating risks, developing and implementing risk management measures in further research.

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